

Assessing Medical Imaging Students' Knowledge of Radiation Protection and Curriculum Coverage in Palestinian Universities

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Abstract

The understanding of radiation protection among workers in radiography fields can significantly influence their conduct during work, thus affecting the standard of medical care. This research examines the knowledge of Ionized Radiation Protection (IRP) among medical imaging students in Palestine and evaluates the coverage of radiation protection topics in their study curriculum. A cross-sectional study was conducted involving medical imaging students from four Palestinian universities. 128 students participated by completing a well-designed questionnaire. The study sample comprised masters, fourth-year, and third-year bachelor's students from medical imaging departments at Palestinian universities, with a response rate of 91.4%. The participants exhibited adequate overall knowledge regarding radiation protection safety, with a mean score of 3.49. However, their understanding of modern imaging procedures was found to be unsatisfactory. Many participants expressed the belief that the level of radiation protection education they received was insufficient. Additionally, most Palestinian medical imaging students reported that their university curriculum lacked coverage of modern radiography topics such as PET scan, fluoroscopy, and nuclear medicine, with mean perception scores of 2.61, 2.69, and 2.81, respectively. Students at lower educational levels demonstrated lower levels of knowledge about IRP. Lack of specialized knowledge between medical imaging students regarding IRP could adversely affect their future professional requirements. Therefore, it is crucial for decision-makers in Palestinian universities and the health sector to develop new strategies aimed at enhancing awareness and knowledge of IRP through targeted training programs. Further research expanding on this study is recommended to explore these issues in greater depth.

Introduction

Recently, the utilization of Ionizing Radiation (IR) in health care practices for medical and therapeutic intent has experienced significant growth. Radiology, in particular, plays a crucial role in modern medicine, with many diagnostic and interventional procedures involving exposure to IR, such as Computed Tomography (CT), fluoroscopy, radiography, and angiography [1, 2]. However, the use of radiation in radiology departments is associated with potential hazardous effects on biological systems, particularly with long-term exposure or high doses of radiation [3, 4]. Studies conducted on radiology workers have indicated that they may experience various health issues, including thyroid disorders, eye diseases, and hair loss [5, 6].

It has been observed that X-rays utilized in endoscopy procedures can impact the structure of DNA molecules within cells, which play a vital role in the body's biological functions. This radiation directly affects cells by breaking chemical bonds within nucleic acids, leading to harmful mutations in DNA molecules. Additionally, IR indirectly contributes to the creation of free radicals by the degradation of H₂O particles, resulting in serious health complications [7, 8]. Recent studies have also indicated that exposure to IR from medical imaging, even in low doses, carries the potential risk of causing cancer [9, 10].

Therefore, it is crucial to make sure that radiation is used responsibly and legally [11]. Assessing the appropriateness of IR exposure in medical imaging is a collective responsibility shared among physicians,

More Information

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Ionizing Radiation Protection, Medical Imaging, Cancer, Computed Tomography, X-rays, Fluoroscopy.

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radiologists, radiology technicians, and other professionals in the field of radiation who involved in imaging technology, directly or otherwise. Additionally, patients themselves bear a responsibility in this regard [12]. As individuals holding scientific degrees conferred by accredited higher educational institutions, they are presumed to possess a sufficient level of scientific knowledge regarding protection from IR and measures ensuring public safety. They are also tasked with disseminating awareness of the optimal use of IR among departmental staff, patients, and the public [12].

It is estimated that there are over two million individuals worldwide engaged in activities related to radiation, with approximately half of them being exposed to man-made IR [13]. Medical procedures utilizing IR, such as nuclear medicine examinations, CT scans, and fluoroscopy-guided interventions, have significantly advanced medicine, leading to enhanced medical decision-making and patient care [14]. According to the National Council on Radiation Protection (NCRP), the average radiation exposure of the US population resulting from medical diagnostic procedures increased sevenfold from the early 1980s to 2006, primarily due to the expanded usage of nuclear medicine and CT [15], making it the largest source of man-made radiation-exposure. However, this raise in exposure has stabilized in the past decade [16].

Numerous studies worldwide have evaluated the knowledge of Ionizing Radiation Protection (IRP) among various groups, including doctors, students, radiology workers, and other healthcare professionals. Generally, these studies concluded that knowledge of the radiation hazard connected with common imaging steps among these groups was limited and varied [17-21]. Radiography students, who are exposed to IR during their training in radiation centers or university laboratories, have been the subject of few studies [22]. In the West Bank, the Palestinian government supervises 437 medical imaging centers run by 370 radiology technicians [23]. Previous studies have indicated low awareness and knowledge of the possibility hazards linked with radiological checking among medical practitioners in Palestine [23, 24]. However, it has not yet been determined to what extent Palestinian radiology technicians are aware of these risks.

The World Health Organization (WHO) advocates for continuous training, practical courses, and regular refresher courses, emphasizing the necessity of specific training in IR in addition to foundational training. These measures are deemed essential for mapping the present situation of awareness [25, 26]. In the West Bank, six Palestinian universities offer bachelor's and master's programs in medical imaging: Al-Quds University (AQU), Palestine Ahliya University (PAU), An-

Najah National University (ANNU), Palestine Polytechnic University (PPU), and Hebron University (HU), Arab American University (AAUP). After liaising with the heads of medical imaging departments at these Palestinian universities and reviewing the curriculum for medical imaging on each university's website, we observed minimal disparities in the curricula, particularly in courses related to IRP. Notably, no previous studies had examined students' perceptions of the study plan in each department in Palestine.

The purpose of this study is to assess the knowledge of IRP and potential hazards linked with radiological examinations among Palestinian students studying medical imaging in universities in the West Bank. Additionally, we investigate students' perceptions of the study plan and evaluate the status of radiation protection education in Palestinian universities.

Materials and Methods

This survey employed a quantitative and descriptive way. Its objective was to establish connections between variables and examine hypotheses regarding the impact of one or more independent factors on dependent variables. This methodology enabled the systematic description of the attributes of the population under study using numerical data [27].

Study Sample

The study targeted masters, third and fourth-year bachelor's students in the medical imaging departments of four universities in Palestine: AQU, ANNU, PAU, and AAUP. However, students from the medical imaging departments at HU and PPU in the West Bank were not included. These universities have recently obtained accreditation, and most of their students are in the first and second years of their bachelor's degree programs. Consequently, there are no master students nor third or fourth-year students enrolled at the time of conducting this study.

Study Tool

Following a thorough examination of online resources and a comprehensive literature review [28-30], an online item-based questionnaire was developed. It served as a tool to assess the knowledge concerning IRP from the perspective of students enrolled in medical imaging departments in Palestine. Furthermore, the questionnaire aimed to investigate students' perceptions of the radiography curriculum offered at Palestinian universities.

The validity of the primary questionnaire content was assessed through a peer review approach utilizing the pretesting method. The questionnaire was presented to six reviewers who were department academic experts in the curriculum in their respective medical imaging departments.

The final version of the study tool comprised three sections with a total of 22 items. Among these, seven

questions were designed to evaluate knowledge and awareness regarding IRP, while 12 questions were dedicated to assessing students' perceptions of the radiography curriculum in their departments. Additionally, three questions were included to gather personal and demographic information about the students, namely university, educational stage, and gender (refer to Tables 1 and 2). Prior to distributing the questionnaire to the entire sample, a pilot survey involving ten students was conducted to identify and address any potential issues that may arise during the survey period.

The final questionnaire was disseminated to 140 students via an email link. The survey commenced in October 2023 and lasted for two months. Following two reminders, a total of 128 completed questionnaires were collected.

Statistical Analysis

The data collected from the studied population (n = 128) underwent analysis using SPSS version 22. Frequency distribution and mean reports were utilized, along with inferential statistics such as ANOVA variance analysis and t-tests. Additionally, a preliminary examination of measurement reliability and internal consistency was conducted using Cronbach's Alpha.

Results

The results indicate that responses were obtained from 128 out of the targeted 140 students across all medical imaging departments (including those in the 3rd, 4th, and master's grades) in the West Bank, Palestine, yielding a response rate of 91.4%. The alpha values for the section evaluating students' awareness and knowledge toward IRP were 0.805, while for the section focusing on students' perceptions about the radiography curriculum the alpha value was 0.929. Both values exceeded the threshold of 0.70, which is commonly used as a criterion [31], indicating satisfactory internal consistency.

Overall, the mean score of students' perceptions regarding the curriculum in the medical imaging departments at their universities was 3.04. Students expressed that the curriculum lacked sufficient coverage of topics such as protection from PET scan, fluoroscopic diagnosis, and nuclear medicine, with mean perception scores of 2.61, 2.69, and 2.81, respectively. However, despite these perceived shortcomings, most students reported having sufficient knowledge of radiation protection issues in general.

Data Analysis of the Studied Variables

Figure 1 presents an assessment of students' personal profiles. The attributes considered include gender, university affiliation, and educational stage.

In terms of gender distribution, the majority of respondents were female (53.1%). Among the

educational stages, the largest proportion comprised students final year of the undergraduate program (43.8%), followed by those in their third level of undergraduate studies (36.7%), and lastly, students pursuing master's degrees (19.5%). Regarding university affiliation, (29.7%) of participants were from An-Najah National University (ANNU), (26.6%) from Al-Quds University, (25.8%) from Arab American University in Jenin (AAUJ), and (18.0%) from Palestine Ahliya University (PAU) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Distribution (Percentage) of the Students According to the Gender, University, and Educational Stage Variables

It is typical for samples to consist of a higher proportion of bachelor's degree students compared to post-graduate students. Moreover, the figure indicates that the respondents broadly represent the targeted population of medical imaging students (including those in the 3rd, 4th, and master's grades) in Palestine.

Students' Knowledge toward IRP

The data obtained from medical imaging students enrolled in Palestinian universities regarding their knowledge of IRP were analyzed and are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 reveals that the overall score for participant's knowledge of IRP was notable, with an average of 3.49 and SD of 0.59. The results also indicate that questions (1, 5-6) pertaining to general knowledge of IRP and X-ray procedures received the highest evaluation rates from medical imaging students. Conversely, questions (3-4) concerning Radiation Protection Advisors (RPA) and their roles, as well as adherence to IRP standards in Palestine, received the lowest evaluation rates.

Table 1: Analysis of Students' Knowledge toward IRP

#	Questions	Mean	SD
1.	How familiar are you with the concept and/or implementation of radiation protection in general?	3.87	0.74
2.	How familiar are you with the concept and/or technology implementation of operating room, which is radiation safe?	3.43	0.92
3.	How familiar are you with the concept of Radiation Protection Adviser (RPA) and his work	2.96	0.99
4.	In general, what is the extent of compliance with the standards of protection from radiation in Palestine?	2.73	0.90
5.	To what extent do you possess the scientific knowledge and skills that make you able to work as a radiographer?	3.99	0.86
6.	How familiar are you with the concept and/or technology implementation of X-Ray?	3.98	0.74
7.	How familiar are you with the diseases that you consider a direct consequence of radiation exposure?	3.48	0.87
Overall score for this section		3.49	0.59

Students' Perceptions about the Radiography Curriculum

The data obtained from medical imaging students enrolled in Palestinian universities regarding their perceptions of the radiography curriculum were analyzed as given in Table (2). Which demonstrates that the overall score for students' perceptions of the radiography curriculum was notable, with a mean of 3.07 and a SD of 0.73. Additionally, the results highlight

that questions (1 and 9) pertaining to training and knowledge regarding radiation hazard, warning signs and X-ray protection received the highest evaluation rates from medical imaging students. Conversely, questions regarding the inclusion of topics linked to IRP of nuclear medicine, PET, and fluoroscopy in the study plan received the lowest evaluation rates from students.

Table 2: Analysis of Students' Perceptions about the Radiography Curriculum in the Palestinian Universities

#	Questions	Mean	SD
1.	I obtained training and knowledge of X-Ray protection	3.73	0.86
2.	I obtained training and knowledge of the concept of protection from Ultrasound	2.85	1.12
3.	I obtained training and knowledge of the concept of protection from CT	3.24	1.09
4.	I obtained training and knowledge of protection from Nuclear Medicine	2.81	1.20
5.	I obtained training and knowledge of protection from PET scan	2.61	1.10
6.	I obtained training and knowledge of protection from Magnetic Resonance	3.07	1.09
7.	I obtained training and knowledge of fluoroscopic diagnosis	2.69	1.09
8.	I obtained training and knowledge of protective equipment to be used during fluoroscopy	2.63	1.10
9.	I obtained training and knowledge of radiation hazard warning signs.	3.41	0.91
10.	I obtained training and knowledge of using a dosimeter	3.28	1.01
11.	I obtained training and knowledge of using personal radiation monitoring device	3.23	1.08
12.	In general, how satisfied are you with the knowledge and training in the field of radiation protection at your university?	3.29	0.96
Overall score for this section		3.07	0.79

Findings According to the Studied Variables

The responses of the participants in this study were analyzed based on personal variables such as students'

gender, university affiliation, and educational stage. The results are presented in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3: Analysis of Students' Knowledge toward IRP and their Perceptions about the Radiography Curriculum According to Gender and University Variables

Field	Gender	Frequency	Average	SD	F	(Sig)
Students' knowledge toward IRP	Male	60	3.60	0.60	0.003	0.954
	Female	68	3.40	0.56		
	Total	128	3.54	0.58		
	Male	60	3.21	0.82	0.377	0.541

Students' perceptions about the radiography curriculum	Female	68	2.95	0.75		
	Total	128	3.10	0.79		
Field	University	Frequency	Average	SD	F	(Sig)
Students' knowledge toward IRP	AAUJ	33	3.47	0.53	0.799	0.496
	Al Quds	34	3.56	0.59		
	ANNU	38	3.54	0.68		
	PAU	23	3.34	0.48		
	Total	128	3.49	0.57		
Students' perceptions about the radiography curriculum	AAUJ	33	3.26	0.93	2.359	0.075
	Al Quds	34	2.99	0.78		
	ANNU	38	3.17	0.71		
	PAU	23	2.73	0.66		
	Total	128	3.07	0.79		

Table 4: Analysis of Students' Knowledge toward IRP and their Perceptions about the Radiography Curriculum According to Educational Stage

Field	Educational Stage	Frequency	Average	SD	F	(Sig)*
Students' knowledge toward IRP	3rd grade	47	3.05	0.52	40.488	0.000*
	4th grade	56	3.61	0.37		
	Master	25	4.03	0.53		
	Total	128	3.49	0.59		
Students' perceptions about the radiography curriculum	3rd grade	47	2.67	0.63	11.487	0.000*
	4th grade	56	3.27	0.73		
	Master	25	3.38	0.89		
	Total	128	3.07	0.79		

Note: * Statistically significant at $p < 0.01$, degrees of freedom (df) = 128

It is evident from Table 3 that the results supported the hypothesis that there are no notable variation ($P < 0.05$) between the averages of students' responses concerning gender and university affiliation in terms of their knowledge of IRP and their perceptions of the radiography curriculum.

Table 4 clearly indicates a notable variation ($P < 0.01$) in the averages of students' responses based on the educational stage variable. This disparity is observed both in terms of students' knowledge of IRP and in terms of their perceptions of the radiography curriculum. Specifically, master's degree students exhibit the highest mean knowledge score toward IRP (4.03) compared to fourth-grade and third-grade undergraduate level students. Similarly, master's students also demonstrate the highest mean scores in the domain of students' perceptions regarding the radiography curriculum (Table 4).

Discussion

The goal of this study is to evaluate and underscore the knowledge of IRP through medical imaging students from Palestinian universities, along with evaluating the coverage of radiation protection topics in their study plans. Three specific areas were identified where medical imaging students perceive inadequacy in their study plans: protection from IR hazards related to PET, fluoroscopy, and nuclear medicine tests.

The results of this research appeared a good overall level of knowledge between participants regarding IRP, as indicated by average score of 3.49. Similar studies, such as Maharjan et al. [32], have also reported adequate knowledge among radiographers and medical imaging students. However, participants exhibited unsatisfactory knowledge regarding modern imaging procedures. While students demonstrated high knowledge levels regarding traditional radiography, such as X-rays, their understanding of modern technologies in IRP, including the risks associated with PET scans, fluoroscopy, and nuclear medicine, was comparatively lower. These results diverge from those of Jha et al. [33], who found only average knowledge of radiation risks between employees, both technical and nontechnical in radiology departments and highlighted issues of negligence in X-ray imaging. Number of scientific papers have confirmed the need for radiographers to enhance their knowledge of IRP cases [23, 34].

The classification of participants according to educational stage and gender indicates that the majority of medical imaging students are female, undergraduates, with master's students comprising the smallest percentage (19.5%). This distribution is affected by the lack of master's programs in medical imaging at certain universities, such as ANNU and PAU,

as well as the lower requests for postgraduate education compared to undergraduate one in Palestine. However, the university affiliation and gender of medical imaging students did not significantly influence their knowledge of IRP or their perceptions of the radiography curriculum. This finding aligns with the observations of Maharjan et al. [32], suggesting that educational opportunities are equally available to both genders without discrimination. Additionally, the geographic distribution of universities across the West Bank facilitates accessibility for students, particularly females, thereby minimizing obstacles related to movement risks due to the occupation.

However, educational stage significantly influenced students' knowledge of IRP and their perceptions of the radiography curriculum. Master's students displayed better knowledge of IRP compared to 3rd and 4th level bachelor's students, likely due to their completion of the undergraduate radiography curriculum and enrollment in advanced postgraduate courses. Conversely, third-year bachelor's students may not have completed the full study plan and may not have been exposed to certain courses offered in the fourth year of their studies. This finding is consistent with a study by O'Sullivan et al. [17], which showed that medical students in clinical radiology education programs demonstrated greater knowledge of radiation exposures compared to students following regular programs.

Study Limitations

This study has several limitations. Firstly, it did not involve academic staff from medical imaging departments in Palestinian universities. The decision was made because faculty members may possess different perspectives and biases towards the curriculum in their departments. Unlike the study by Faggioni et al. [35], which included a broader spectrum of participants, this research focused solely on third and fourth-year students, along with master's students in medical imaging, from four universities in the West Bank of Palestine. Additionally, students from Gaza were not included in the study, which limits the ability to make comparisons across different categories such as medical students, radiologists, and other academic classifications across all Palestinian universities. Exploring these aspects could be an interesting extension of this study and may warrant further investigation.

Conclusion

Our research reveals that graduating medical imaging students from Palestinian universities tend to overestimate their knowledge of IRP issues based on a basic level survey. However, they express dissatisfaction with the content of their study plans, noting a lack of coverage on various topics, particularly IRP associated with modern imaging procedures.

Despite their perceived proficiency, these students acknowledge that their current knowledge of IRP for most imaging procedures is insufficient to meet their future professional needs. Objective assessments also reveal gaps in their understanding, particularly concerning nuclear medicine, PET, and fluoroscopy. Given the recent expansion of medical imaging technologies and the growing workforce in this sector, our findings underscore the need for enhanced education and greater proficiency in these areas.

Based on our results, we strongly advocate for concerted efforts to improve education and knowledge in IRP, especially in relation to modern medical imaging technologies such as fluoroscopy, PET, and nuclear medicine. We recommend that decision-makers within the Accreditation and Quality Assurance Commission for Higher Education in Palestine prioritize the revision and reassessment of radiography programs in Palestinian universities. This should involve the inclusion of new courses on radiation protection to address these gaps.

Furthermore, we suggest that university leaders and healthcare authorities in Palestine focus on raising awareness and knowledge of IRP through specialized training programs for professionals in the field and recent graduates from medical imaging departments. This proactive approach will ensure that future radiography professionals are adequately equipped to navigate the challenges posed by evolving medical imaging technologies and safeguard patient safety effectively.

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Conflict of Interests

Author declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1]. Yurt A, Cavuşoğlu B, Günay T. Evaluation of awareness on radiation protection and knowledge about radiological examinations in healthcare professionals who use ionized radiation at work. *Mol Imaging Radionucl Ther.* 2014;23(2):48-53. doi: 10.4274/mirt.00719
- [2]. Bercovich E, Javitt MC. Medical Imaging: From Roentgen to the Digital Revolution, and Beyond. *Rambam Maimonides Med J.* 2018;9(4): e0034. doi: 10.5041/RMMJ.10355

- [3]. Kamiya K, Ozasa K, Akiba S, Niwa O, et al. Long-term effects of radiation exposure on health. *Lancet*. 2015;386(9992):469-78. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(15)61167-9
- [4]. Sharma M, Singh A, Goel S, et al. An evaluation of knowledge and practice towards radiation protection among radiographers of Agra city. *Sch J App Med Sci*. 2016;4:2207–2210. doi: 10.36347/sjams.2016.v04i06.070
- [5]. Brent GA. Environmental exposures and autoimmune thyroid disease. *Thyroid*. 2010;20(7): 755-61. doi: 10.1089/thy.2010.1636
- [6]. Hammer GP, Scheidemann-Wesp U, Samkange-Zeeb F, et al. Occupational exposure to low doses of ionizing radiation and cataract development: A systematic literature review and perspectives on future studies. *Radiation and Environmental Biophysics*. 2013;52(3):303-19. doi: 10.1007/s00411-013-0477-6
- [7]. Johnson RH. The role of the radiation safety specialist as witness: risk communication with attorneys, judges, and jurors. *Health Phys*. 2001;81(6):661-9. doi: 10.1097/00004032-200112000-00016
- [8]. Rahman N, Dhakam S, Shafqut A, et al. Knowledge and practice of radiation safety among invasive cardiologists. *J Pak Med Assoc*. 2008;58(3):119-22
- [9]. Little MP, Wakeford R, Tawn EJ, et al. Risks associated with low doses and low dose rates of ionizing radiation: why linearity may be (almost) the best we can do. *Radiology*. 2009; 251(1):6-12. doi: 10.1148/radiol.2511081686
- [10]. Brenner DJ, Doll R. Cancer risks attributable to low doses of ionizing radiation: assessing what we really know David, *Adv. Exp. Med. Biol*. 2016. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-39406-06
- [11]. Park MY, Jung SE. Patient Dose Management: Focus on Practical Actions. *J Korean Med Sci*. 2016;31:S45-54. doi: 10.3346/jkms.2016.31.S1.S45
- [12]. European Society of Radiology (ESR), European Federation of Radiographer Societies (EFRS), (2019) Patient Safety in Medical Imaging: a joint paper of the European Society of Radiology (ESR) and the European Federation of Radiographer Societies (EFRS). *Insights Imaging*;10: 45. doi: 10.1186/s13244-019-0721-y
- [13]. Erkan I, Yarenoglu A, Yukseloglu EH, et al. The investigation of radiation safety awareness among healthcare workers in an education and research hospital. *Iranian Journal of Radiation Research*. 2019;17:455-461. doi: 10.18869/acadpub.ijrr.17.3.447
- [14]. National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (NASEM) Division on Earth and Life Studies; Nuclear and Radiation Studies Board; Committee on Developing a Long-Term Strategy for Low-Dose Radiation Research in the United States. *Leveraging Advances in Modern Science to Revitalize Low-Dose Radiation Research in the United States*. Washington (DC): National Academies Press (US) (2022), *Low-Dose Radiation Exposures and Health Effects*. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK586463>. Accessed December 28th, 2024.
- [15]. National Council on Radiation Protection and Measurements (NCRP). NCRP Report No. 160, Ionizing Radiation Exposure of the Population of the United States. Bethesda, MD, National Council on Radiation Protection and Measurements. 2015. Available at: <https://ncrponline.org/publications/reports/ncrp-report-160/>. Accessed December 28th, 2024.
- [16]. National Council on Radiation Protection and Measurements (NCRP). Report No. 184 – Medical Radiation Exposure of Patients in the United States. Bethesda, MD, National Council on Radiation Protection and Measurements. 2019. Available at: <https://ncrponline.org/shop/reports/report-no-184-medical-radiation-exposure-of-patients-in-the-united-states-2019/>. Accessed December 28th, 2024.
- [17]. O'Sullivan J, O'Connor OJ, O'Regan K, et al. An assessment of medical students' awareness of radiation exposures associated with diagnostic imaging investigations. *Insights Imaging*. 2010; 1(2): 86-92. doi: 10.1007/s13244-010-0009-8
- [18]. Wong CS, Huang B, Sin HK, et al. A questionnaire study assessing local physicians, radiologists and interns' knowledge and practice pertaining to radiation exposure related to radiological imaging. *Eur J Radiol*. 2012;81(3):24. doi: 10.1016/j.ejrad.2011.02.022
- [19]. Günalp M, Gülünay B, Polat O, et al. Ionizing radiation awareness among resident doctors, interns, and radiographers in a university hospital emergency department. *Radiol Med*. 2014;119(6): 440-7. doi: 10.1007/s11547-013-0374-8
- [20]. Khalilia WM., (2025). Evaluation of radiographers knowledge about radiation safety and cancer risks of ionizing radiation exposure. *The American Journal of Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Research*, 2025;7(1):6-14. doi: 10.37547/tajmspr/Volume07Issue01-02
- [21]. Najjar RH, Alsulaiman AM, Alraddadi JS, et al. Assessment of Physicians' Knowledge and Awareness about the Hazards of Radiological Examinations on the Health of Their Patients at a Tertiary Care Hospital, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *Cureus*. 2022;14(7):e27479. doi: 10.7759/cureus.27479
- [22]. Paolicchi F, Miniati F, Bastiani L, et al. Assessment of radiation protection awareness and knowledge about radiological examination doses among Italian radiographers. *Insights Imaging*. 2016;7(2):233-42. doi: 10.1007/s13244-015-0445-6
- [23]. Hamarsheh A, Amro A. Knowledge and awareness of radiation hazards among Palestinian radio technologists. *East Mediterr Health J*. 2017; 23(8):576-580

- [24]. Hamarshah A, Ahmead M. Assessment of physicians' knowledge and awareness about the hazards of radiological examinations on the health of their patients. *Eastern Mediterr Health J*. 2012;18(8):875-81. doi: 10.26719/2012.18.8.875
- [25]. Workshop on Efficacy and Radiation Safety in Interventional Radiology (1995: Neuherberg, Germany). (2000). Efficacy and radiation safety in interventional radiology. World Health Organization. Available at: <https://iris.who.int/handle/10665/42290>
- [26]. Shabani F, Hasanzadeh H, Emadi A, et al. Radiation Protection Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice (KAP) in Interventional Radiology. *Oman Med J*. 2018;33(2): 141-147. doi: 10.5001/omj.2018.26
- [27]. Nassaji, H. Qualitative and descriptive research: Data type versus data analysis. *Language Teaching Research*. 2015;19(2): 129–132. doi: 10.1177/1362168815572747
- [28]. Goula A, Chatzis A, Stamouli MA, et al. Assessment of Health Professionals' Attitudes on Radiation Protection Measures. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021;18(24):13380. doi: 10.3390/ijerph182413380
- [29]. Ashkanani H, AlDallal Y, Almajran A, et al. Radiology in the Undergraduate Medical Curriculum: The Student Perspective. *Med Princ Pract*. 2022;31(5):486-492. doi: 10.1159/000525496
- [30]. Yashima S, Chida K. Awareness of Medical Radiologic Technologists of Ionizing Radiation and Radiation Protection. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2022;20(1): 497. doi: 10.3390/ijerph20010497
- [31]. Taber KS. The use of Cronbach's alpha when developing and reporting research instruments in science education. *Research in Science Education*. 2018;48(6):1273-1296 doi: 10.1007/s11165-016-9602-2
- [32]. Maharjan S, Parajuli K, Sah S, et al. Knowledge of radiation protection among radiology professionals and students: A medical college-based study. *Eur J Radiol Open*. 2020;7: 100287. doi: 10.1016/j.ejro.2020.100287
- [33]. Jha RK, Nayak R, Subramanian N. Knowledge, attitude and practice of radiation risk among employees in selected hospitals of Nepal. *Janaki Med. Coll. J. Med. Sci*. 2017;4(2). doi: 10.3126/jmcjms.v4i2.17071.
- [34]. Zervides C, Sassis L, Kefala-Karli P, et al. Assessing radiation protection knowledge in diagnostic radiography in the Republic of Cyprus. A questionnaire survey. *Radiography*. 2020;26(2):E88-E93. doi: 10.1016/j.radi.2019.11.003.
- [35]. Faggioni L, Paolicchi F, Bastiani L, et al. Awareness of radiation protection and dose levels of imaging procedures among medical students, radiography students, and radiology residents at an academic hospital: Results of a comprehensive survey. *Eur J Radiol*. 2017;86:135-142. doi: 10.1016/j.ejrad.2016.10.033

